

AMMONIA IN SALINE SOLUTIONS

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Preface

The present report is the formal product of my work on obtaining the master degree in chemistry. The project has been carried out under careful supervision by Thorvald Pedersen, University of Copenhagen, Britta Pedersen, Danish National Environmental Research Institute (NERI) and Bo Jönsson, University of Lund. In terms of appreciation I'd hate to distinguish between you as all the help and guidance you have given has been outstanding. So I will just restrict myself to say: Thanks!

Also, I would like to thank Bjarne Jensen and Kjeld Sauerberg from NERI for always helping out on technical issues. The last part of this project has mainly been carried out at laboratory 5 at the H.C. Ørsted institute. Here I will like to thank the staff and fellow students - especially Malene Ringkjøbing Jensen for proof reading the report.

Abstract

In the present work ammonia in natural waters has been examined. To determine the chemical properties of ammonia (and many other species) in saline solutions, we have developed a computer model capable of estimating activity coefficients at various sea salt concentrations. The obtained results have shown excellent agreement with experimental data as well as with other more empirical models.

Furthermore, we have developed an apparatus capable of measuring gas solubilities in aqueous solutions at different temperatures. Using this technique we have determined the Henry's law constant of ammonia in pure water and found very good agreement with data obtained by other workers.

Field work carried out in Holland has been used to investigate oceanic processes influencing the gaseous/aqueous ammonia level in the North Sea. This study has indicated that the ocean may be an important source of ammonia for the atmosphere.

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Symbols and abbreviations

a	Activity
β	$1/kT$
c	Molar concentration (mol/l)
Cl	Chlorinity (‰)
d	Density
ϵ_r	Relative dielectric constant
f	Fugacity
γ	Molal activity coefficient
H	Henry's law constant
I	Ionic strength
k_s	Setchenow constant (kg/mol) (= salting coefficient)
K	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant
K^{st}	Stoichiometric equilibrium constant
M	Molecular weight
m	Molal concentration (mol/kg)
μ	Chemical potential
N_a	Avogadro's number
p	Pressure
R	Gas constant
σ	Hard sphere radius (Å)
s	Standard error
S	Salinity (‰)
T	Temperature (K)
v	Stoichiometric number
y	Molar activity coefficient
z	Valence
CDH	Corrected Debye-Hückel
FIA	Flow Injection Analysis
IPB	Indophenol Blue

MC	Monte Carlo
MPN	Meetpost Noordwijk (Platform)
MSA	Mean Spherical Approximation
NBS	National Bureau of Standards
NERI	National Environmental Research Institute
NH _x	NH ₃ + NH ₄ ⁺
NO _x	NO ₂ + NO ₃
NO _y	NO _x + HNO ₃ + NO ₃ ⁻
OPA	<i>o</i> -phthaldialdehyde

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Many attempts have been made to mimic the molybdenum containing nitrogenase because it effectively converts dinitrogen at very mild conditions. In contrast, the Haber-Bosch cycle [2] currently used on the industrial scale requires high pressure and temperature and thereby increasing the cost of fertilizers. However, the research has not yet resulted in any economically competitive alternative to the Haber-Bosch cycle, but it has been made clear that molybdenum does not play the key role first thought.

Another natural route to active nitrogen is by thunderstorms in the upper troposphere. The high electrical discharge formed by lightning can ionize dinitrogen which reacts with oxygen under the formation of nitric oxide, NO. This compound shows an extensive atmospheric chemistry and is an important participant in the catalytic cycle of ozone destruction. Nitrogen oxides are also formed from dinitrogen when burning fossil fuels. At high combustion temperatures the reaction

becomes important and catalytic filters are used to remove oxides from vehicle exhaust gases.

Biological utilization

The nitrogen fixing paths mentioned above supply the N-cycle with reactive species ready to participate in biological systems. This involves the inter-conversion of ammonia and NO into many other nitrogen compounds such as nitrate, nitrite, amino acids etc. As a discussion of all possible biological reactions is out of the scope of this work, only the most important will be mentioned here.

Ammonium is formed when nitrogen is fixed by nitrogenase. By *nitrification* soil bacteria oxidize this to nitrate available for plants to absorb. The reverse reaction, *ammonification*, occurs during the decay of organic material - compounds containing nitrogen are transformed to ammonia and thereby enables the cycle to repeat. As both nitrate and ammonium are highly soluble in water, they constitute an environmental problem when they are present in excess concentrations. Leaching during rain fall results in migration of these species to other ecosystems. In Denmark, nitrate leaching from fields represents a significant nitrogen loss of 30% and thus results in an equivalent input to the bordering freshwater systems.

If the cycle balance, the active nitrogen species will eventually end up, yet again, as dinitrogen. One natural process of producing dinitrogen is by *denitification*. This reaction is carried out by organisms living both in soils and in the oceans. By reducing nitrate into elemental nitrogen, these organisms obtain energy vital to their existence. Denitrification from agricultural fields is around 8%, but the environmental consequences are not significant because the main product is inactive nitrogen. However, not all nitrate is completely converted into dinitrogen as the reduction may cease at oxidation state +1 under the formation of nitrous oxide, N₂O.

Nitrous oxide is a rather inert gas, but as it eventually enters the stratosphere it is photolysed into dinitrogen and nitric oxide. In fact 90% of the NO present in the stratosphere is formed this way. Because of its high inertness N₂O has a residence time of 120 years as it only slowly leaves the troposphere due to the low vertical mixing rate. This combined with the fact that it is a very effective greenhouse gas, results in a global warming potential 300 times larger than that of CO₂. It has been estimated that the level of nitrous oxide has increased 15% since preindustrial time.

Deposition

Nitrogen species present in the atmosphere can deposit to aquatic and terrestrial systems. Ammonia and nitric acid are both very soluble in water and are removed from the atmosphere during rain fall - either in their pure forms or as their common salt, ammonium nitrate. Ammonia often originates from ground level agricultural sources and is subject to direct interactions with the surface layers. For example, when a package of air containing ammonia passes a water surface, the two-phase system will seek equilibrium by either dissolving or releasing ammonia in/from the aqueous phase. As both ammonia and nitric acid show acid-base properties, the pH of the surface layer plays an important role and to quantify such reactions, detailed knowledge of flux rates and equilibrium constants is required. The estimated wet deposition to the North Atlantic ocean is evenly distributed between NO_y and NH_x and amounts to 620 Gmol N/yr - or nearly 9% of the total input. However, these estimates are subject to large uncertainties as several authors [3, 4, 5] have pointed out that the ocean itself may emit ammonia. More on this issue in Chapter 6.

References: [6, 7, 8]

Chapter 2

Properties of sea water

2.1 Introduction

Sea water being a multi-component solution differs significantly from ideal mixtures and special consideration is therefore required to describe the physical/chemical properties. This chapter deals mainly with the properties needed within the scope of this project and seeks to deal with specific problems encountered during the experimental and modeling work.

2.2 Composition

Sea water contains a variety of different electrolytes (Table 2.1) whose overall concentration may vary. However, for over a century it has been known that the relative concentrations of the individual species remain practically unchanged for all the oceans [9]. Therefore, it is possible to define the composition of sea water by a widely used measure called the salinity S . The definition of salinity is the total mass (in grams) of dissolved inorganic matter in one kilogram of sea water, after the amount of carbonate species have been converted to oxides and halogens to chlorine. Organic matter is removed.

Because of this definition the measurements were tedious and difficult to perform whence another measure, the chlorinity Cl was defined as grams of chlorine in one kilogram of sea water. The major advantage of this approach is its easy determination using silver nitrate titration. During the first half of the 20'th century the relation between salinity and chlorinity was based on the following equation by Forch *et al.* [10]

$$S = 1.805Cl + 0.030 \quad (2.1)$$

However, this relation is not satisfactory because chlorinity and salinity should be directly proportional. Therefore Equation 2.1 was later replaced by the more accurate definition [11]

$$S = 1.80655 \cdot Cl \quad (2.2)$$

Today the salinity is obtained by measuring the electric conductivity, which is closely related to the number of ions present in the solution. Another classic measure of dissolved electrolytes is the ionic strength I defined as

$$I = \frac{\sum z_i^2 m_i}{2} \quad (2.3)$$

where z_i and m_i are the valency and molality of the ion i , respectively. The ionic strength is an important property as it is a measure of the overall charge density in the medium. Taking advantage of the constant relationship between

ION	$\frac{m}{(\text{mol/kg})}$	ION	$\frac{m}{(\text{mol/kg})}$
Na ⁺	0.48525	SO ₄ ²⁻	0.02927
Mg ²⁺	0.05519	Br ⁻	0.00087
Ca ²⁺	0.01064	F ⁻	0.00006
K ⁺	0.01058	HCO ₃ ⁻	0.00241
Sr ²⁺	0.00009	B(OH) ₃	0.00044
		Cl ⁻	0.56579

TABLE 2.1: Ionic composition of natural sea water at $S=35\%$.

ions in sea water, formulas as the following may be used to convert salinity into ionic strength

$$I = \frac{19.9273 \times S}{1000 - 1.00511 \times S} \quad (2.4)$$

For further details about salinity, consult the monography Chemical Oceanography, 1975 [12].

2.3 Artificial sea water

The most authentic medium applicable to examine the chemical properties of sea water, must be natural water collected from the oceans. However, real sea water has some clear disadvantages that will cause practical problems and render the experiments very difficult to reproduce.

When dealing with measurements of ammonia it is important to recognize the presence of microorganisms. These may produce or consume aqueous ammonia and effectively disturb the $\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$ equilibrium. Of course this is unacceptable and the organisms must be removed by filtration or by some form of sterilization (heat, mercury etc.). Another cause for concern is that although the composition of sea water is in principle uniform throughout the oceans, minor regional deviations may occur. These matters can be dealt with, but they greatly complicate the measurements and so another approach is chosen. A vast collection of more or less adequate recipes of artificial sea water have been compiled by Bidwell and Spotte [13].

Since it is difficult to measure $p\text{H}$ in sea water [14], it is preferable to investigate compositions with no acid-base properties. In this way only ammonia is contributing to $p\text{H}$ and knowledge of the dissociation constant enables the calculation of c_{H^+} . Clegg and Whitfield [15] have estimated the dissociation constant of ammonia in artificial sea water using the Pitzer model. Their sea water composition includes only the major ions (99.5%) found in natural waters and so they omit carbonate, borate etc. As it is the intention to apply this dissociation constant in the experiments, this composition is chosen. The recipe originates from Dickson [16] and has the composition shown in Table 2.2. Other studies [17, 18] have been based on very similar recipes.

SPECIES	$\frac{m}{(\text{mol/kg})}$	SALT	$\frac{m}{(\text{mol/kg})}$	$\frac{c}{(\text{mol/l})}$
Na^+	0.48618	NaCl	0.42764	24.99
Mg^{2+}	0.05474	Na_2SO_4	0.02927	4.15
Ca^{2+}	0.01075	KCl	0.01058	0.78
K^+	0.01058	MgCl_2	0.05474	5.21
Cl^-	0.56920	CaCl_2	0.01075	1.19
SO_4^{2-}	0.02927			

TABLE 2.2: The composition of Dickson's artificial sea water at $S = 35\%$, $I = 0.7225 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$.

To calculate the molalities and ionic strength at different salinities, Dickson gives the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} m(S) &= \frac{m(S=35) \times I(S)}{I(S=35)} \\ I(S) &= \frac{19.919 \times S}{1000 - 1.00198 \times S} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

The justification of formulas for such a seemingly simple task, is that molality is defined as moles per kg of pure solvent whereas salinity is defined as grams per kg sea water.

2.4 Activity and vapor pressure of water

Information on the vapor pressure of water over saline solutions is required when measuring the solubility of ammonia as it affects the partial pressure of an initially dry, calibrated NH_3 -gas (Chapter 4). In this section an expression is evaluated to determine the water vapor pressure as a function of salinity and temperature.

Activity of water

Electrolytes solvated in water will, primarily via electrostatic forces, affect the surrounding water molecules and hence their activities. The extend of this effect depends on which species are present in the solution. As the salinity is a well defined measure of these species it will indeed be useful to know the water activity as a function of salinity and temperature. In the following section this function is evaluated using colligative properties of sea water. The freezing point depression of sea water has been determined experimentally at different salinities [19]. We shall now use these

data to calculate the activity of water a_w based on the following considerations:

At the freezing point a dynamic equilibrium between the solid and liquid phase exists. In terms of chemical potentials this is written as

$$\mu_{w(l)} = \mu_{w(s)} \quad (2.6)$$

Assuming the dissolved ionic species do not mix with the solid phase, the chemical potentials for the two phases are

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{w(l)} &= \mu_{w(l)}^\ominus + RT \ln a_w \\ \mu_{w(s)} &\approx \mu_{w(s)}^\ominus \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Keeping in mind that the free energy change of freezing is given by

$$\mu_{w(l)}^\ominus - \mu_{w(s)}^\ominus = \Delta_{\text{fus}}G = \Delta_{\text{fus}}H - T\Delta_{\text{fus}}S \quad (2.8)$$

the activity of water can thus be obtained by combining the above equations:

$$\ln a_w = \frac{\Delta_{\text{fus}}H}{-RT} + \frac{\Delta_{\text{fus}}S}{R} \quad (2.9)$$

For pure water $\ln a_w = 0$, $T = 273.15$ K and Equation 2.9 rearranges to

$$\frac{\Delta_{\text{fus}}S}{R} = \frac{\Delta_{\text{fus}}H}{R \times 273.15} \quad (2.10)$$

The depression of the freezing point, $\Delta T = T - 273.15$ is assumed to be small so that

$$\left(\frac{1}{273.15} - \frac{1}{T} \right) = \left(\frac{T - 273.15}{T \times 273.15} \right) \approx \frac{\Delta T}{273.15^2} \quad (2.11)$$

Combining this with (2.9) and (2.10) the final relation between a_w and ΔT can be written as

$$\ln a_w = \frac{\Delta_{\text{fus}}H}{R} \frac{\Delta T}{273.15^2} \quad (2.12)$$

Formally (2.12) is valid only at the freezing point, but according to Vignati [20] the activity of water is fairly constant in the range of normal sea water temperatures (0-25°C). Using Equation 2.12 to calculate water activities as a function of salinity a linear fit has been carried out ($0 \leq S \leq 35$):

$$a_w = 1 - (0.000522641 \pm 5.404 \times 10^{-6}) \times S \quad (2.13)$$

Sverdrup *et al.* [21] have also proposed an empirical expression which gives the water activity as a function of chlorinity. This equation is based on measurements of vapor pressure and is easily expressed in terms of salinity (using Equation 2.2)

$$a_w = 1 - 0.000969 \times Cl = 1 - 0.0005367 \times S \quad (2.14)$$

It is seen that this result is in very good agreement with the expression derived from the freezing point depression data.

Yet another source of a_w is the osmotic coefficient, ϕ , which has been calculated using Monte Carlo simulations (Chapter 3). The relation between the water activity and the osmotic coefficient is [22, page 438]:

$$\ln a_w = -\phi M_w^{\text{aq}} \sum m_i \quad (2.15)$$

This shows excellent agreement with Equation 2.13 and 2.14. These simulations also yield the temperature dependence of a_w which is less than 0.01% from 273 K to 298 K and so confirms the above assumption by Vignati. Figure 2.1 shows plots of the activity of water at different salinities calculated by Equations 2.13, 2.14 and 2.15. As a comparison activities in NaCl-solutions [23] have also been included.

It is seen that the various data sets are quite similar at low salinities, but as the electrolyte becomes more concentrated minor differences arise. The activity of water has decreased by around 2% at 35‰ and thus the effect of salinity is only of minor importance.

FIGURE 2.1: The activity of water as a function of salinity.

Vapor pressure of water

From the equations derived above it is now possible to calculate the vapor pressure of water p as a function of salinity by the relation

$$p = a_w \times p^\ominus \quad (2.16)$$

which applies under ideal gas conditions. p^\ominus is the vapor pressure of pure water at a specific temperature. The temperature dependence of p^\ominus can be expressed by the Clausius-Clapeyron equation

$$\frac{d \ln p}{dT} \approx \frac{\Delta_{vap} H}{RT^2} \quad (2.17)$$

As shown in Figure 2.2 the temperature has the most pronounced effect on the vapor pressure, while the salinity is much less important. For convenience, a contour plot of the same data is shown in Appendix A and should be useful in determining the vapor pressure of sea water.

2.5 Activity coefficients

Definition and purpose

Activity coefficients are used to describe free energy deviations relative to a chosen standard state. For aqueous solutions the most common choice of state is that of infinite dilution (*i.e.* ideal behavior). In terms of the chemical potential μ an ideal and real solution may be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i^{\text{ideal}} &= \mu_i^\ominus + RT \ln m_i \\ \mu_i^{\text{real}} &= \mu_i^{\text{ideal}} + \mu_i^{\text{excess}} \\ &= \mu_i^\ominus + RT (\ln m_i + \ln \gamma_i) = \mu_i^\ominus + RT \ln a_i \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

The excess potential $RT \ln \gamma_i$ is the difference in chemical potential between the real and standard state and so defines the activity coefficient γ_i . It follows from Equation 2.18 that that activity coefficient may also be written as

$$\gamma = \frac{a}{m} \quad (2.19)$$

In the limit of infinite dilution the excess potential must approach zero

$$\gamma \rightarrow 1 \text{ as } m \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.20)$$

The majority of sea water present in the oceans has an ionic strength of 0.7 mol/kg which is far from infinite dilution. Therefore, in order to investigate chemical equilibria in natural waters one can no longer use the concentration scale,

FIGURE 2.2: Vapor pressure of water in saline solution plotted as a function of temperature and salinity.

but activities have to be applied. And this is where the activity coefficients comes in as they describe the relationship between a and m .

An equivalent procedure is to convert the thermodynamic equilibrium constant into a stoichiometric one

$$K^{\text{st}} = \prod_i m_i^{v_i} = K \times \prod_i \gamma_i^{-v_i} \quad (2.21)$$

which is *not* constant but varies with composition and concentration. Thus K^{st} must be evaluated for each specific solution. This latter approach is often found in the literature on marine chemistry where the stoichiometric constant is typically given as a function of salinity and temperature.

Concentration scales

The activity coefficient is defined relative to a specific concentration scale (molar, molal etc.) and conversion between the scales must be considered when comparing different sets. For example, the Pitzer model yields coefficients on the molal scale while methods of statistical mechanics typically give values on the molar scale. This particular conversion is carried out using the following expression [24]

$$\gamma = y \times \frac{c}{md_0} \quad (2.22)$$

where γ and y are the molal and molar activity coefficient, respectively. c is the molarity, m the molality and d_0 the density of the pure solvent. For a multicomponent solution the relation between molar and molal scale can be written as follows [22]

$$\frac{c}{m} = d - \sum_i c_i M_i \quad (2.23)$$

Here d is the density of the solution, c_i and M_i are the molarity and molecular weight of species i , respectively. Using these relations one obtains the final expression for converting activity coefficients from molar to molal scale

$$\gamma = y \times \left(\frac{d - \sum_i c_i M_i}{d_0} \right) \quad (2.24)$$

Therefore, in order to interconvert the two one needs to know the composition and density of the solution. For artificial sea water the composition is well known, but the density is often not and therefore must be either measured or estimated using density tables of real sea water.

Ionic species

As ions carry an electric charge they are subject to long-range Coulomb forces which leads to substantial deviations from ideality. The potential between two ions of opposite charge is proportional to $1/r$ and falls off much less rapidly

than for example the Van der Waal potential proportional to $1/r^6$. Due to the complexity of describing the excess potential arising from electrostatic interactions, most of Chapter 3 has been devoted to this subject.

Neutral species

Neutral species like NH_3 , CO_2 , O_2 etc. are not affected by Coulomb forces which leads to much less deviation from ideality compared to ionic species. However, short range interactions do have an influence and minor deviations occur. Millero [25] has set up an empirical relation for the calculation of the activity coefficient of a non-electrolyte specie in sea water ($S=35\%$, $T=25^\circ\text{C}$) when its solubility in sodium chloride solution is known

$$\ln \gamma_i = 0.0938 + 0.3404 \times k_s \quad (2.25)$$

Here k_s is the Setchenow parameter (see page 24) for species i in sodium chloride solution. According to Millero, fitting to experimental measurements yields a standard error of 0.014. Using this formula it is possible to convert the extensive collection of solubility data for NaCl solutions to sea water. Setchenow parameters for ammonia in sodium chloride solution have been derived from two different sources, and by applying (2.25) the sea water activity coefficients shown in Table 2.3 are obtained.

T (K)	k_s (kg/mol)	γ_{NH_3}	REF.
298.15	0.076	1.13	[26]
313.15	0.048	1.12	[27]
353.15	0.048	1.12	[27]

TABLE 2.3: Activity coefficients of ammonia in sea water at $S=35\%$ and 25°C estimated from Setchenow parameters using Equation 2.25.

Thus, there is an increase in the activity coefficient which will produce a *salting out effect*. That is, the solubility of ammonia will decrease with increasing salinity. Equation 2.25 requires Setchenow parameters at 25°C while the data from reference [27] are in the range $40\text{-}80^\circ\text{C}$. Even though these values show no temperature dependence in this region the value at 25°C is still uncertain.

Another estimate of the activity coefficients of ammonia and ammonium in sea water has been made [22] using the Pitzer model:

$S/(\%)$	5	15	25	35	40
γ_{NH_3}	1.00	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.02
$\gamma_{\text{NH}_4^+}$	0.759	0.667	0.621	0.592	0.580

TABLE 2.4: Activity coefficients of ammonia and ammonium in sea water at 25°C calculated using the Pitzer model.

Also, in connection with studies of air/sea exchange, Quinn *et al.* [5] use the following expression to calculate the activity coefficient of ammonia

$$\gamma = 1 + 0.085 \times I \quad (2.26)$$

which gives a coefficient of 1.06 at 35% and 298 K. A comparison of the above activity coefficients for ammonia in sea water show deviations of 11%, indicating that further investigation is required. Using a newly developed simulation approach, this has been done in Chapter 3.

2.6 pH in sea water

Originally Sørensen defined pH as $-\log a_{\text{H}^+}$ and still today this is the definition recommended by IUPACC and is known as the NBS scale. To measure pH_{NBS} , glass electrodes calibrated using buffer solutions of low ionic strength are normally applied. In sea water samples, the ionic strength may be as high as 0.8 mol/kg so that the liquid junction potential of the electrode is affected. The pH value thus obtained is *not* equal to $-\log a_{\text{H}^+}$ but rather should be regarded as an arbitrary operational number. Still, it may be a useful measure for studying non-thermodynamic properties.

Alternatively one may use the free hydrogen scale where pH is definitined as follows

$$pH_{\text{F}} = -\log m_{\text{H}^+} \quad (2.27)$$

Here H^+ is the free hydrogen ion - *i.e.* protons not tied up in protonated species (except H_3O^+). The electrode calibration is performed using saline buffers containing a known amount of acid. However, because sea water contains sulfate, inevitable hydrogen sulfate is formed and so to derive the free proton concentration, knowledge of the dissociation constant for H_2SO_4 is required.

This leads to the third definition tailored specifically to saline samples: the sea water scale, also known as the Hansson or total hydrogen scale.

$$pH_{\text{sws}} = -\log\left(c_{H^+} + c_{\text{HSO}_4^-}\right) \quad (2.28)$$

Here the protonation of sulfate is explicitly accounted for enabling a consistent set of saline buffer solutions. This operational definition is indeed useful, but when applied one must ensure that all association/dissociation constants are converted to this scale.

As revealed by the above discussion the measurement of pH in sea water samples is not a trivial task and great care should be taken when relating the results to thermodynamic properties.

2.7 Solubility of gases

Henry's law

The solubility of a gas X may be described by the heterogeneous gas-liquid equilibrium

having the thermodynamic equilibrium constant

$$K = \frac{a_{X(aq)}}{f_{X(g)}} = \frac{\gamma_{X(aq)}c_{X(aq)}}{f_{X(aq)}} \quad (2.29)$$

which is indeed a constant and varies *only* as a function of temperature. At ideal conditions (low pressure and low concentration) the activity coefficient is unity and the fugacity is equal to the partial pressure. Therefore (2.29) simplifies to

$$K \approx \frac{c_{X(aq)}}{p_{X(g)}} \equiv H \quad (2.30)$$

which is equivalent to the well known Henry's law [28]. In sea water the air above the surface is generally taken to be ideal ($f = p$), but the concentration of solutes is too high to allow the assumption of an ideal aqueous phase. Therefore activity coefficients must be considered. Some gaseous species, including ammonia, participate in acid-base reactions that affect the overall solubility

In these cases it is useful to apply the *effective Henry's law constant* which includes the total aquatic concentration of the dissolved gas. For ammonia $c_{\text{NH}_x} = c_{\text{NH}_3} + c_{\text{NH}_4^+}$ and the stoichiometric effective constant is given by

$$H_{\text{eff}}^{\text{st}} = \frac{c_{\text{NH}_x}}{p_{\text{NH}_3}} = H^{\text{st}} \left(1 + \frac{c_{H^+}}{K_a^{\text{st}}}\right) \quad (2.31)$$

Please refer to Tables 3.8 and 3.9 for values of H^{st} and K_a^{st} as a function of salinity.

Temperature dependence

As with any other thermodynamic equilibrium constant the temperature dependence may be expressed using the van't Hoff equation:

$$\frac{d \ln K}{d(1/T)} = -\frac{\Delta_{\text{soln}}H}{R} \quad (2.32)$$

which, assuming $\Delta_{\text{soln}}H$ is independent of temperature, integrates to

$$K(T_2) = K(T_1) \times \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta_{\text{soln}}H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right)\right) \quad (2.33)$$

For gases $\Delta_{\text{soln}}H < 0$ and so the solubility always decreases with increasing temperature.

Setchenow parameters

Another way of expressing the solubility of non-electrolytes in ionic solutions is by the Setchenow equation [29, 30]:

$$\ln \frac{H}{H^{\text{st}}} = \ln \gamma_i = k_s \times m \quad (2.34)$$

where k_s is the Setchenow parameter also known as the salting coefficient. H and H^{st} are the Henry's law constant in pure water and in the electrolyte solution, respectively. Hence, from this relation the activity coefficient of a given non-electrolyte γ_i can be estimated at different ionic concentrations m . Note the choice of logarithmic scale. In older literature base 10 is often applied [26] while newer papers [25] use the natural logarithm. More on the molecular interpretation of the Setchenow relation can be found on page 27.

Chapter 3

Modeling activity coefficients

3.1 Introduction

The classical approach used to estimate activity coefficients in electrolyte solutions is the well-known theory of Debye and Hückel proposed in 1923. This method is very simple to apply and at its best accounts for solutions of ionic strength up to 0.1 mol/kg. However, the ionic strength in sea water ranges from 0-0.7 mol/kg and the Debye-Hückel theory is therefore inadequate. The widely used model of Pitzer extends the Debye-Hückel theory with a set of empirical parameters which enable the calculation of activity coefficients in very concentrated solutions (10 mol/kg), but requires a large number of “interaction parameters”. More recently Lund *et al.* [31, Appendix F] have applied Monte Carlo simulations on sea water solutions and have successfully described the activity coefficients on a more accurate basis. This chapter provides an introduction to the Debye-Hückel theory as well as to the Pitzer model, while the Monte Carlo simulations will be described in greater detail.

3.2 The primitive model of electrolytes

The Debye-Hückel theory as well as our Monte Carlo method are based on a dielectric continuum model where particles (ions and non-electrolytes) are treated as hard spheres with radii, σ_i and valencies, z_i while the nature of the solvent is described solely by the temperature dependent dielectric constant ϵ_r . The potential energy of a particle i interacting with another particle j is described using Coulomb’s law subject to the following conditions,

$$u(r_{ij}) = \begin{cases} \frac{z_i z_j e^2}{4\pi\epsilon\epsilon_r r_{ij}} & r_{ij} \geq \sigma_i + \sigma_j \quad (\text{long range}) \\ +\infty & r_{ij} < \sigma_i + \sigma_j \quad (\text{short range}) \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Here r_{ij} is the distance between the two particles, ϵ is the dielectric permittivity of vacuum and e is the elementary charge. The sum of the hard sphere radii, $\sigma_i + \sigma_j$ can be regarded as the distance of closest approach. At large separation, for example between two cations, this sum becomes negligible. Obviously, as the solution becomes more concentrated the distances between particles are decreased. This leads to a higher contribution from short-range interactions and hence the importance of the hard sphere radii is increased.

Treating the solvent as a structure-less medium containing hard spheres is of course an approximation but, as will be shown in a short while, a fairly good one.

3.3 Debye-Hückel theory

Debye and Hückel’s theory proposed in 1923 became a milestone in the exploration of electrolyte solutions as it explained the activity coefficients by a purely theoretical approach. Prior to this only empirical relations existed; for example hard experimental labor by Brønsted yielded the expression:

$$\ln \gamma = -\alpha\sqrt{m} - 2\beta m \quad (3.2)$$

where α today can be derived from the Debye-Hückel theory. Normally the theory of Debye-Hückel is presented as the limiting- and the extended law shown in Equation 3.3.

$$\ln \gamma_{\pm} = \begin{cases} -|z_+ z_-| \cdot A\sqrt{I} & (\text{limiting law}) \\ \frac{-|z_+ z_-| \cdot A\sqrt{I}}{1+B\sqrt{I}} & (\text{extended law}) \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

The parameter B present in the extended law includes the hard sphere radii, but is to be regarded as an entirely empirical parameter. By adjusting B it is possible to predict activity coefficients in solutions of $I \sim 0.1$ m. In the

limiting law B is set equal to zero and so neglects all hard sphere contributions. Thereby it limits the range of ionic strength to $I < 0.01$ mol/kg.

As mentioned above the theory is based on the primitive model, but in order to reach the simple formulas shown in Equation 3.3 Debye and Hückel made several approximations. The essential assumption of the model is that of an uniform *ionic atmosphere* surrounding any given central ion. This atmosphere arises from a continuous density function creating a charged spherical haze:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho &= \sum_i q_i c_i e^{-q_i u(r)/kT} \\ &\approx \sum_i q_i c_i - \sum_i \frac{c_i q_i^2 u(r)}{kT} + \sum_i \frac{c_i q_i^3 u(r)^2}{2k^2 T^2} + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (3.4)$$

where q_i and c_i are the charge and concentration of ion i , respectively. $u(r)$ is the potential energy relative to the bulk solution and by applying the Poisson equation¹ on (3.4) the electric potential ψ is obtained. However, the mathematical complexity of doing so made the evaluation impossible and so the full expression was expanded as shown. Due to electroneutrality the first sum in the expansion is zero. The second term is included in the differential while the rest are *omitted*.

These are the assumptions and approximations of the Debye-Hückel theory and the reason of failure at high ionic strength. As will be shown later, brute force calculations in the dielectric continuum model correctly account for the non-ideal behavior of strong electrolyte solutions and therefore corroborate the primitive model.

3.4 Pitzer's equations

A widely used method to estimate activity coefficients in electrolyte solutions is the ionic interaction approach originally developed by Pitzer [32, 33]. Normally this method is referred to as the ‘‘Pitzer model’’ and in its general form the excess potential is expressed as

$$G^{ex}/RT = f(I) + \sum_i \sum_j m_i m_j \lambda_{ij}(I) + \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k m_i m_j m_k \mu_{ijk} + \dots\quad (3.5)$$

where $f(I)$ is a Debye-Hückel term taking into account long range interactions. λ_{ij} and μ_{ijk} are two and three body ‘‘interaction parameters’’, respectively and describe short range contributions. Only for very concentrated solutions is it necessary to include four body interaction terms, but in the case of sea water these are not required. The model is semi-empirical and in practice the parameters are determined from available experimental data of activity coefficients in simple electrolyte solutions.

Sea water contains six major ionic species (Table 2.1) and so a large number of parameters are required in Equation 3.5. To estimate the activity coefficient of a given cation M in natural waters Clegg and Whitfield [22] give the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}\ln \gamma_M &= z_M^2 F + \sum_a m_a (2B_{Ma} + ZC_{Ma}) \\ &+ |z_M| \sum_c \sum_a m_c m_a C_{ca} \\ &+ \sum_c m_c (2\Phi_{Mc} + \sum_a m_a \psi_{Mca}) \\ &+ \sum_a \sum_{a' < a} m_a m_{a'} \psi_{Maa'} \\ &+ 2 \sum_n m_n \lambda_{Mn} + 3 \sum_n m_n^2 \mu_{Mnn} \\ &+ 6 \sum_n \sum_{n' < n} m_n m_{n'} \mu_{Mnn'} \\ &+ 6 \sum_n \sum_a m_n m_a \zeta_{Mna} \\ &+ 6 \sum_n \sum_c m_n m_c \eta_{Mnc}\end{aligned}\quad (3.6)$$

where the first term is a classical Debye-Hückel function and the subscripts c , a and n represent cations, anions and neutral species, respectively. The terms B , C and the Greek letters are functions specific to the given solution and some of them vary with ionic strength and temperature. As revealed by (3.6) the determination of sea water activity coefficients using the Pitzer model is rather tedious and requires a large number of empirical data. However, much work has been done using this approach and it has described the activity coefficients for most species present in sea water.

For a more thorough discussion as well as a historical review of the Pitzer model the reader should consult Millero's monography [34].

3.5 Monte Carlo simulation

In contrast to the Debye-Hückel theory where the distribution of charge is approximated by an ionic atmosphere, the primary goal of the Monte Carlo method is to find this distribution by simulating the positions of the ions in solution. In connection with the development of nuclear weapons, Metropolis *et al.* [35] developed the Monte Carlo method

¹ $\nabla^2 \psi = -\frac{4\pi\rho}{\epsilon}$

used here to simulate the electrolyte solution. This method makes heavy use of randomly generated numbers and so it has adopted the name of the famous gambling city.

The simulation is performed by a computer model where the solution is mimicked by a cubic box containing hard, charged spheres subject to the rules of the primitive model (Eq. 3.1). Initially the particles are randomly added to the box until the composition wanted has been reached. Next, particles are moved - one at the time - to new random positions. After each move the total Coulomb energy U is calculated by adding all particle interactions

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N u(r_{ij}) \quad (3.7)$$

If the energy is lowered after one such move, the configuration is accepted. If on the other hand the move leads to an energy increase, the configuration is accepted with the probability $\exp(-\beta\Delta U)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta U < 0 & \quad \text{Accept move} \\ \Delta U > 0 & \quad \text{Accept if } \xi < \exp(-\beta\Delta U) \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where ξ is a random number between 0 and 1. In this way the particle distribution is simulated and as the Monte Carlo “game” proceeds, U reaches a stable value and the system is assumed to represent equilibrium.

On the front page of this report the reader may enjoy a snapshot of a simulation box mimicking oceanic water ($S=35\%$).

Widom’s method

After the system is equilibrated the calculation of activity coefficients can begin. The displacement of particles is continued, but at every step a particle α of interest is inserted at a random position. This allows calculation of the energy required to add the particle to the system which, by definition, is equal to the chemical potential

$$\mu_\alpha = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_\alpha} \right)_{p,T,N} \quad (3.9)$$

According to Widom’s method [36] the excess chemical potential can be expressed as

$$\beta\mu_\alpha^{\text{ex}} = -\ln \langle \exp[-\beta\Delta U_\alpha(\mathbf{r})] \rangle \quad (3.10)$$

where the term enclosed in angular brackets is the “Widom average”. That is, the average energy change of adding the particle. After each calculation the inserted particle is removed from the box and hence has not disturbed the system. It is interesting to note that in the case of neutral particles ΔU is either 0 or $+\infty$ (Eq. 3.1) and thus the exponential term in the Widom expression becomes either 1 or 0. For example:

$$\langle \exp[-\beta\Delta U_\alpha(\mathbf{r})] \rangle = \frac{0 + 0 + 1 + 0 + \dots}{n} \quad (3.11)$$

where n is the total number of insertions. This shows that the chemical potential is related to the *probability* of finding a vacant place for the particle. It is clear that in more concentrated solutions it will become more and more difficult to find room for the particle and thus, the excess potential ($RT \ln \gamma$) is increased. Turning to the Setchenow equation (Eq. 2.34) we see that a simple linear relationship between $\ln \gamma$ and the concentration is assumed - the salting coefficient k_s being the proportional constant.

For ionic species it has been shown [37] that the original Widom method becomes less accurate. This is due to the fact that electroneutrality in the cell is violated by adding a charged particle. To solve this problem Svensson *et al.* [38] have proposed a modified Widom technique which applies charge scaling:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta\mu_\alpha^{\text{ex}}(r) &= -\ln \langle \exp[-\beta\Delta U_\alpha^{sr}(r)] \rangle \\ &+ \int_0^1 \frac{\langle \beta\Delta U_\alpha^{el}(r) \exp[-\beta\{\Delta U_\alpha^{sr}(r) + \lambda\Delta U_\alpha^{el}(r)\}] \rangle}{\langle \exp[-\beta\{\Delta U_\alpha^{sr}(r) + \lambda\Delta U_\alpha^{el}(r)\}] \rangle} d\lambda \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

Here the particles are rescaled to maintain electroneutrality and the particle energies are *not* perturbed by the inserted particle. The modified Widom approach is of course an approximation, but as the box size and hence the number of particles are increased it becomes more and more exact. This technique has previously been applied on complex systems where it has produced good results [39].

FIGURE 3.1: Solvation of ions by primary (A) and secondary (B) hydration shells. (D) and (E) show overlap.

	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻
σ_{cryst}	1.2	1.5	0.7	1.1	1.7	2.4
σ_{Stokes}	1.8	1.3	3.5	3.1	1.2	2.3

TABLE 3.1: Crystallographic- and Stokes radii (in Ångström) of the major sea water ions.

Hard sphere radius

As stated in the primitive model of electrolytes the particles (ions and non-electrolytes) are treated as hard spheres. In the Monte Carlo simulation the particle radii are applied whenever a *move* or an *insertion* is performed. All new randomly generated positions are tested for collision with other particles and, if true, properly dealt with. In connection with particle movement (*i.e.* in the Monte Carlo game) overlapping configurations are not allowed and all moves that lead to overlap are discarded. However, when calculating the excess potential using Widom's method, overlap is included in the average (as $\Delta U = +\infty$) and as shown in the previous section the activity coefficient of a neutral molecule can be related to the probability of success of inserting a particle.

The hard sphere assumption is of course an approximation. Ions in solution are solvated and enclosed by one or more shells of solvent molecules (here water), which is by no means bound to be organized in a spherical way. Furthermore, when two real ions meet their overall hydration sphere may become smaller *i.e.* some of the solvent molecules are lost. Figure 3.1 pictures the hydration of ions in solution and shows the idea of non-additive ionic radii where the hydration shell is decreased.

It is to be noted that ionic strength and temperature will affect the hydration and in the framework of the Mean Spherical Approximation (MSA), radii are described as a function of concentration. At the conditions of natural waters these effects are assumed to be negligible.

The extent of solvation is dominated by charge/radius properties of the solute; small, highly charged ions will effectively distort the medium and attract more water molecules than larger ions with equal charge. Thus the hydrated radius of Na⁺(aq) will be larger than that of K⁺(aq). The opposite trend is seen in the crystallographic radius. Also, due to the polar properties of water, anions are expected to be much less solvated than cations and thus they have radii closer to their crystallographic radii.

A commonly used method to estimate the effective ionic radii in solution is by measuring the ionic mobility. Stokes equation describes the frictional force F of a sphere of radius r and speed v moving through a fluid with viscosity η . This combined with the ionic mobility u yields a measure of the hydrated radius of the ion - namely the Stokes radius σ_{Stokes} :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} F &= 6\pi\eta\sigma v \\ u &= \frac{|Z|ev}{F} \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \sigma_{\text{Stokes}} = \frac{|Z|e}{6\pi\eta u} \quad (3.13)$$

The Stokes radius can now be calculated from values of the ionic mobilities and the results thus obtained agree with the qualitative model described above. The solvated sodium ion is indeed found to be larger than the solvated potassium ion (Table 3.1).

These values of the Stokes radii have been used in the Monte Carlo simulations, but did not yield acceptable results. A reasonable explanation of this can be the fact that the hard sphere radius obtained from Stokes equation is derived from the frictional force as the ion move through the liquid. The primitive model uses the hard sphere radius to limit the distance between ions. These are two different regimes and the Stokes radii can be used as a qualitative guideline only.

As outlined above it is difficult to estimate the value of the hard sphere radius as it is actually *not* hard and differs with the solution conditions. Therefore, in lack of a stringent procedure describing ions in terms of hard spheres, we have chosen to determine the radii by applying mean activity coefficient data from single electrolyte solutions.

An ensemble is constructed to mimic a solution of a single electrolyte and the hard sphere radii are adjusted to yield mean activity coefficients equal to experimental determined values. It turns out that it is the distance of closest approach (sum radius) that is important - *i.e.* the sum of the cat- and anion radius. For example, when simulating a NaCl-solution, equal results are obtained by setting the individual sizes of Na^+ and Cl^- (in Ångström) to 1.0/2.5 and 2.0/1.5, respectively. As long as the sum is 3.5 Å.

In this way a number of relevant salts have been examined in the range $I=0.1-0.8$ mol/kg as shown for the sodium salts in Figure 3.2.

FIGURE 3.2: Calculated (lines) and experimental (circles) mean activity coefficients in single electrolyte solutions.

Abbes *et al.* [40] have made similar investigations using a corrected Debye-Hückel (CDH) theory which yields very similar results as this work. The results of the data fittings using Monte Carlo simulations are shown in Table 3.2 along with available sum radii obtained using the corrected Debye-Hückel approach.

METHOD	NaCl	KCl	CaCl ₂	MgCl ₂	HCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
Monte Carlo	3.5	3.2	4.5	4.7	4.2	3.4
CDH	3.4	3.1	4.4	-	-	

TABLE 3.2: Sum radii (in Ångström) fitted to experimental data.

As the aim is to simulate a sea water solution containing many different ions, there is a need to divide the sum radii into individual ionic contributions. Based on the assumption that anions are only weakly hydrated [41], the radius of the chloride ion is now fixed to its crystallographic radius. This somewhat arbitrary choice is used to obtain the remaining ion sizes which are readily calculated as shown in Table 3.3.

$\sigma/(\text{Å})$	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NH ₄ ⁺	H ⁺
MC	1.8	1.5	3.0	2.8	1.7	1.6	1.5	2.5
MSA	1.9	1.7	3.2	2.9	1.5	1.5		

TABLE 3.3: Hard sphere radii of individual ions in sea water obtained from Monte Carlo simulations (MC) and the Mean Spherical Approximation (MSA).

Instead of reinventing the wheel let's for a moment turn to work already done. The mean spherical approximation (MSA) has previously been used to describe sea water [42] and an extensive database of ionic radii is available. Also

shown in Table 3.3 are values from the MSA and using these in the Monte Carlo simulation yield very similar results as with the radii obtained by fitting to experimental data. As this discovery were made at a late stage of the project, the radii first found are used throughout the rest of the simulations presented here.

Neutral particles

In order to investigate non-electrolytes (CO_2 , NH_3 etc.) in sea water, appropriate values of the hard sphere radii must be obtained. Since a neutral particle is not affected by Coulomb forces its hard sphere radius is the *only* parameter determining the deviation from ideality. To find the radius of a given non-electrolyte α , a simulation of a single Widom particle in sodium chloride solution is performed. As illustrated in Figure 3.3, the size of the Widom particle is adjusted until the model yields results equal to experimental data (Setchenow constants). The radii thus obtained are now used to obtain activity coefficients in sea water solution by the usual Widom procedure.

FIGURE 3.3: Method to determine the activity coefficient of a non-electrolytes α in sea water by applying the Setchenow constant for sodium chloride solution.

By this technique we have simulated Setchenow constants as a function of the hard sphere radius as shown in Figure 3.4. Therefore, by obtaining the solubility of the neutral molecule in sodium chloride solution the size of the Widom particle is easily determined. Table 3.4 shows the overall results from simulations of a number of neutral molecules in sodium chloride and sea water solution. As for ammonia, the activity coefficient has never been measured and comparison is therefore not possible. However, on page 22 we found (via empirical methods) values of γ_{NH_3} ranging from 1.01 to 1.13. Our result of $\gamma_{\text{NH}_3}=1.05$ closely resembles these values and, considering the simplicity and clear theory of the Monte Carlo approach, this model conquers. In addition, the conditions in the simulation box (temperature, pressure etc.) can easily be changed. This flexibility is completely absent in Millero's formula (Eq. 2.25), but might be incorporated in the Pitzer model - if enough interaction parameters are available, that is.

FIGURE 3.4: Simulated Setchenow constant k_s in sodium chloride as a function of the hard sphere radius σ of a neutral particle α .

	SODIUM CHLORIDE				SEA WATER		
	k_s^{exp}	k_s^{calc}	Δ	$\sigma/(\text{\AA})$	γ^{exp}	γ^{calc}	Δ
O ₂	0.312	0.319	0.007	2.2	1.221	1.207	0.014
N ₂ O	0.245	0.248	0.003	1.9	1.225	1.161	0.064
CO ₂	0.201	0.209	0.006	1.7	1.169	1.135	0.034
H ₂ S	0.155	0.158	0.003	1.4		1.101	
NH ₃	0.076	0.072	0.004	0.8		1.054	

TABLE 3.4: Calculated and measured activity coefficients of non electrolytes in sea water ($S=35\%$, 25°C). The hard sphere radii are obtained by data fitting of Setchenow constants in sodium chloride solution.

Single ion activity coefficients

A major advantage of modeling activity coefficients, is that it allows the computation of single ion activity coefficients otherwise difficult to obtain by experimental means. The demand of macroscopic electroneutrality renders the addition of single ions practically impossible, and only mean activity coefficient data can be obtained by measuring the change in chemical potential when adding neutral salts.

The excess potential of a single ion simulated with the Monte Carlo method can be regarded as the sum of an electrostatic- and hard sphere contribution, respectively. The derivation of the electrostatic term is based on Coulomb's law and is thus purely theoretical. In contrast, the hard sphere contribution is dependent of the choice of the individual particle radii. On page 29 the radius of the chloride ion was assumed equal to its crystallographic size which is a somewhat arbitrary choice.

It is clear that as the solute concentration is decreased, the hard sphere contribution becomes less important and in Debye-Hückel's limiting law these contributions are completely ignored. Figure 3.5 shows how electrostatic and hard sphere forces are contributing to the overall excess potential at various sea salt concentrations.

FIGURE 3.5: Hard core (HC) and electrostatic (EL) contributions to the total activity coefficient (TOT) of the chloride ion in sea water calculated with the Monte Carlo method.

From the simulations of sea water a number of ionic activity coefficients at various salinities have been derived. To express these in a shorthand manner the data have successfully been fitted to Equation 3.14.

$$\ln \gamma_i = aS + bS^{0.5} + cS^{1.5} \quad (3.14)$$

where S is the salinity in per mille. The parameters a , b , and c are listed in Table 3.5 and are valid in the range $0 \leq S \leq 35\text{‰}$ at 298 K.

	a	b	c	s
Na^+	0.0205532	-0.159354	-0.000986596	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$
K^+	0.0194030	-0.162823	-0.000979393	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Mg^{2+}	0.1071180	-0.664265	-0.006752640	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Ca^{2+}	0.1041940	-0.670623	-0.006511840	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Cl^-	0.0205745	-0.157099	-0.000879540	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$
SO_4^{2-}	0.1000860	-0.738175	-0.005971080	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
NH_4^+	0.0194030	-0.162823	-0.000979393	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
H^+	0.0232680	-0.151911	-0.000928230	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$

TABLE 3.5: Results of a fit for single ion activity coefficients cf. Equation 3.14 at 298 K. s is the standard error of the fit.

The Pitzer model also yields activity coefficients for individual ions and a comparison with the Monte Carlo model shows excellent agreement. Table 3.6 lists single ion activity coefficients calculated at different salinities by Monte Carlo simulations and the Pitzer model, respectively.

	$S = 35\%$			$S = 15\%$		
	γ^{MC}	γ^{Pitzer}	Δ	γ^{MC}	γ^{Pitzer}	Δ
Na ⁺	0.642	0.638	0.004	0.689	0.692	0.003
K ⁺	0.617	0.589	0.028	0.676	0.667	0.009
Mg ²⁺	0.206	0.205	0.001	0.256	0.251	0.004
Ca ²⁺	0.186	0.194	0.008	0.242	0.243	0.001
Cl ⁻	0.673	0.692	0.019	0.703	0.724	0.021
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.117	0.100	0.017	0.179	0.169	0.010

TABLE 3.6: Single ion activity coefficients in sea water calculated by Monte Carlo simulation and the Pitzer model at two different salinities.

Mean activity coefficients

As mentioned, only *mean* activity coefficients can be measured. This have been done for a number of salts in saline solutions [43, 44, 45] and also Pitzer model calculations are available [22]. As shown in Table 3.7 very good agreement is found with the values obtained using the Monte Carlo method.

SALT	T/(K)	S/(‰)	γ^{exp}	γ^{MC}	γ^{Pitzer}
Na ₂ SO ₄	298	35	0.374	0.374	0.345
		25	0.405	0.399	0.378
		15	0.435	0.445	0.433
		5	0.620	0.560	0.559
K ₂ SO ₄	298	35	0.385	0.381	0.344
		35	0.352	0.360	0.336
NaCl	298	35	0.672	0.664	0.665
		15	0.730	0.699	0.708
KCl	298	35	0.645	0.645	0.639
CaSO ₄	298	35	0.136 [†]	0.152	0.159 [†]
<i>s</i>				0.023	0.029

TABLE 3.7: Mean activity coefficients in sea water measured and calculated with Monte Carlo simulations and the Pitzer model, respectively. [†]Values from Culberson, 1978.

Examination of the standard error *s* of the two models show that the Monte Carlo approach is somewhat better than the Pitzer model. However, the calculated value for calcium sulfate shows some deviation from the experimental data, which is probably due to “ion pair” formation. As divalent oppositely charged ions strongly attract each other, the dielectric continuum becomes less applicable and effectively ϵ_r is lowered. Currently, no attempts have been made to correct for this effect, but introducing a variable dielectric constant may be a way of getting around the problem. In the framework of the Pitzer model, these matters are frequently dealt with by the inclusion of association constants. In practice, the latter approach could be incorporated into our model, but would violate the very foundation of the theory as statistical mechanics describe equilibrium in terms of distributions. Furthermore, inclusion of association constants would add more parameters to an otherwise simple approach.

In the Pitzer calculations shown in Table 3.7 ion pairing has not been considered and the values are comparable to those obtained from the Monte Carlo method. This is in spite the fact that the MC simulations are using only *one* adjustable parameter (the hard sphere radius) to describe a particle. The Pitzer model requires parameters describing the interactions between all the different ions present and, in that context, is far more complex.

Stoichiometric equilibrium constants

The activity coefficients found using the Monte Carlo model are further validated by solving practical problems encountered in marine chemistry. In Section 2.5 it was outlined how the ionic strength of sea water influences chemical equilibrium, and so suggests the usage of stoichiometric equilibrium constants. As this project is aiming to describe the chemistry of ammonia in sea water, a natural choice to start the investigation is the dissociation of ammonium in sea water:

which in term of the stoichiometric acidity constant K_a^{st} can be described as

$$K_a^{\text{st}} = \frac{m_{\text{NH}_3} m_{\text{H}^+}}{m_{\text{NH}_4^+}} = K_a \times \frac{a_w \gamma_{\text{NH}_4^+}}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (3.15)$$

Here K_a is the dissociation constant valid in pure water *i.e.* the thermodynamic constant. Using the calculated activity coefficients it is now possible to derive the stoichiometric constant as a function of salinity. This has been done earlier by Clegg and Whitfield [15] using the Pitzer formalism and also experimental data are available from Khoo *et al.* [46]. The results of the model calculations are shown in Table 3.8 together with the values of Clegg and Khoo. Here the Pitzer model is slightly better than the Monte Carlo simulation, and it can be seen that the dissociation constant is only subject to minor deviations, which can be understood by examining Equation 3.15; both a_w and γ_{NH_3} are close to unity and so is the fraction $\gamma_{\text{NH}_4^+}/\gamma_{\text{H}^+}$.

Another important issue is the equilibrium existing between gaseous and dissolved ammonia given by the stoichiometric Henry’s law constant

$$H^{\text{st}} = \frac{H}{\gamma_{\text{NH}_3}} \quad (3.16)$$

$S/\text{‰}$	pK_a^{st}		
	Exp.	Pitzer	MC
0	9.245	9.245	9.245
5	9.260	9.259	9.267
15	9.290	9.285	9.301
25	9.320	9.311	9.332
35	9.351	9.337	9.364
s		$1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$

TABLE 3.8: The dissociation constant of ammonium in sea water at 298 K obtained from measurements, the Pitzer model and Monte Carlo simulations.

Experimental values of the stoichiometric constant in sea water are not described in the literature, whereas comparison is not possible. Table 3.9 gives the constant at various salinities calculated using Monte Carlo simulations:

$S/\text{‰}$	0	5	15	25	35
$\frac{H^{\text{st}}}{(\text{M} \cdot \text{atm}^{-1})}$	60.7	60.3	59.3	58.7	57.8

TABLE 3.9: Henry's law constants of ammonia simulated in sea water (298 K) at different salinities.

The thermodynamic constant ($S=0\text{‰}$) on which these calculations are based is taken from Clegg and Brimblecombe [47]. As shown in Table 5.1 on page 45 many other determinations have been made and with quite variable results. Omitting the work of Hales and Dreves, the literature values of H are found to deviate 5-9%. The effect of salinity is less than these variations and so the initial choice of the thermodynamic constant is crucial. To determine which constant in Table 5.1 is the most correct would require a review of the original papers - this is out of the scope of this report.

Chapter 4

Experimental methods

4.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the various methods used in the experimental work. This covers low concentration measurements of aqueous ammonia using flow injection analysis, and the development of an equilibration system used for measurements of Henry's law constants.

4.2 Measurements for ammonia

The OPA method

The setup used for measuring aqueous ammonia during this project is based on a sensitive fluorescence method using Flow Injection Analysis (FIA). FIA was developed in Denmark in the mid seventies and has since proved itself as useful for a variety of different analytical methods. The concepts behind flow injection will not be described here - the reader is referred to a review written by one of the inventors [48]. NERI has build a setup [49] used for low concentration (nanomoles per liter) field measurements. It is a modification of a system originally designed by Jones in 1991 [50] and also Kerouel and Aminot [51] have developed a very similar system based on segmented flow analysis.

The fluorescence method has some clear advantages compared to the often used colorimetric indophenol blue method (page 38) as the detection limit is significantly lower and the use of toxic reagents is minimized. The theory behind the method is based on the reaction of *o*-phthaldialdehyde (OPA) with ammonia to form a complex which, after reduction with sodium sulfite, shows fluorescence¹

This reaction is strongly temperature dependent and suggests means to control the sensitivity. A higher temperature increases the formation of the fluorescent compound and is therefore used to measure in the low concentration range. However, the compound will decompose at temperatures above 90°C thus putting a limit to the sensitivity. Before reaching these vital steps, the sample and the reagents are prepared in the FIA system. Figure 4.1 shows a diagram of the entire system.

In order to measure the total concentration of aqueous ammonia (c_{NH_x}), all ammonium ions must be deprotonated by mixing with sodium hydroxide. However, as sea water contains both magnesium and calcium, unwanted precipitation of hydroxides may occur as *pH* is increased. This problem is handled by the addition of citrate ions, which are strongly complexing with both magnesium and calcium. In this way *pH* can be raised to around 12.4 where more than 99% of the ammonia is on the deprotonated form.

Primary amines present in the saline sample behave just like ammonia and form fluorescent compounds with OPA. Therefore, to remove such species the sample is passed over a Teflon membrane which allows diffusion of NH_3 into a pure aqueous phase. By doing so, all salts and amines in the sea water are filtered off and thereby ruling out interference with the fluorescence process. The effectivity of the membrane is dependent on the salt concentration so that saline standard solutions must be applied when measuring sea water samples. Next, OPA and sulfite are added and the final reaction mixture flows through a thermostated heat coil before it finally enters the fluorescence detector.

¹ $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 335 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 425 \text{ nm}$

FIGURE 4.1: Schematic representation of the OPA flow injection system used at NERI.

To minimize the baseline signal, the sodium hydroxide/citrate reagent must have the lowest possible ammonia concentration. Even though high grade purity chemicals are applied, the ammonia level is still too high to measure in the 10-200 nM range. Therefore further refining is required. This is accomplished by passing the hydroxide/citrate reagent through a diffusion scrubber consisting of a microporous Teflon tube immersed in dilute sulphuric acid. Due to the large diffusion gradient in the Teflon wall, ammonia is effectively transported out of the tube. This online stripping removes about 97% of the ammonia present in the reagent.

A practical problem with the scrubber is the difficulty of connecting the Teflon tube to the PVC-tubes used in the rest of the FIA system. Previously, the two unlike materials had to be connected using special (and expensive) Teflon glue which often leaked. Only one person from the technical staff were able to handle the gluing and so made this a limiting procedure. However, during this project an improved method has been made. This new method (Figure 4.2) is completely glue-free and has proved itself very stable during several field campaigns. The problem with connecting the tubings is the softness of Teflon. It is virtually impossible to push the smaller Teflon tube into the larger PVC tube - unless care is taken to stiffen the soft Teflon. An unfolded paper clip is applied for this purpose as it fits perfectly in the Teflon tube and so offers an excellent "handle" to push together the two tubes.

FIGURE 4.2: Connecting Teflon and PVC tubings: A paper clip (C) is used as a handle to push the Teflon tube (T) into the PVC tube (P).

Other methods

A widely used method for measuring aqueous ammonia in sea water samples is the indophenol blue (IPB) method first described by Berthelot in 1859. The detection limit is around 200 nanomoles per liter and is based on a colorimetric determination of the blue complex, indophenol blue, formed when ammonia reacts with phenol and hypochlorite under alkaline conditions. The sea water level of ammonia can be as low as 20 nanomoles though, so that a more accurate method is required for some types of measurements (for example air-sea exchange experiments). Another issue with the IPB method is the use of relatively toxic chemicals, constituting a potential health risk to the operator. Alternative methods applied on saline samples include ion chromatography [52] and cathodic stripping voltammetry [53]. They will not be discussed any further.

4.3 Stability of samples

Bringing an aqueous sample into equilibrium with gaseous ammonia, involves hours of bubbling during which several measurements need to be made. It is desirable to investigate whether the liquid sample remains stable during this process, since contamination from glassware or the laboratory air could effectively disturb the equilibrium.

The idea is straight forward: The NH_x concentrations of ammonium chloride solutions are monitored over a period of 7-10 hours. During this time possible contamination processes will reveal themselves by a change in the ammonia concentration. Figure 4.3 illustrates the overall trends from these experiments. Both graphs show how the concentration changes in time as the sample is left to stand. The solutions have an initial concentration of $[\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}]=300$ nM and:

- In the first experiment (I) a 2 ml syringe is used to inject eighteen samples and therefore the sample vessel is required to be opened 2×18 times during equilibration.
- In the second experiment (II) sample taking is carried out using a 20 ml syringe and so the sample vessel has to be opened only twice during fifteen injections.

FIGURE 4.3: Two ammonium chloride solutions (300 nM) examined as a function of time. The steps represent the measured deviation from the mean c_{NH_x} concentration. See text for details.

From these experiments it can be seen that the deviation is nearly 20% in the first experiment while only 5% in the second. To evaluate the data statistically, Kendall's correlation test is applied (Appendix C). The results of the two stability experiments are shown in Table 4.1.

SAMPLE	n	τ	$\tau_{P<0.05}$	TREND
I	18	0.673	± 0.346	increase
II	15	-0.124	± 0.390	none

TABLE 4.1: Sample stability determined by Kendall's Correlation analysis using a significance level of 5%. n is the number of measurements in each experiment.

In the first experiment there is a significant increase of the ammonia concentration, probably due to contamination from the laboratory air during sample taking. In the second experiment the air contact has been reduced and the concentration remains stable. Therefore, in order to minimize the uncertainty on the measurements, it is necessary to avoid air-sample contact.

4.4 Gas/liquid equilibration

The two laboratories accomodating the experimental facilities used during this project have no previous setup for measuring gas/liquid equilibrium. Therefore a new equilibration system had to be developed from scratch and the hardships of doing so are described in the present section.

The scope of our “equilibrator” is to have a controlled system where a gaseous compound is in thermodynamic equilibrium with an aqueous phase. By applying a continuous flow of a *calibrated gas* to a water sample, the system will eventually reach equilibrium. As the concentration in the gaseous phase is known, measurements in the liquid phase are sufficient to determine the equilibrium constant (Henry’s law).

Gas dilution

Ammonia in the atmosphere is typically present in levels of parts per billion (ppb). Therefore, to mimic this scenario it is preferable to equilibrate with a gas of similar concentration.

Commercial ammonia/nitrogen mixtures in mixing ratios of parts per million (ppm) are available at a reasonable price, but these levels are still too high compared to the natural conditions. To reach the ppb level, the ppm gas is further diluted using an online dilution box. By mass-flow controllers this device very precisely mixes the initial gas with clean air until the desired concentration is reached. To ensure the precision of the gas dilution box, it is calibrated every half year using standardized mass-flow controllers from the supplier.

Time efficiency

The uptake of gas into the liquid is controlled by diffusion of molecules from the gaseous phase into the surface layer. Fick’s first law describes the kinetics for such a system:

$$F = -D \times \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad (4.1)$$

Here F is the molecular flux, D the molecular diffusion coefficient, C concentration and x is the “wall thickness” as described in the Gradient Flux model [54]. The wall thickness is dependent on the agitation at the surface - that is more turbulence leads to a lower thickness and so increases the flux. The flux is per area and in order to shorten the time to equilibrate, a large surface of contact is required. This can be achieved by bubbling tiny bubbles of gas through the liquid. However, as described in the following section bubbles may cause problems.

A similar approach is to provide a large water surface. By passing the water phase through a container filled with finely cut glass tubings, this is effectively achieved. Simultaneously a stream of gas flows in the opposite direction and so bubbles are completely avoided.

Over saturation

The goal is to measure the thermodynamic solubility of ammonia in water. But it is possible that gas molecules can be trapped in the liquid matrix and so lead to over saturation. This effect varies with the viscosity in the fluid phase and hence the temperature and ionic strength; low temperatures and high salt concentrations cause the liquid viscosity to increase. By keeping the flow at a moderate level, the molecules are able to escape the matrix and establishment of true equilibrium is expected.

Gas flow

The gas flow needs to be controllable and must not be too large as this can cause over saturation as described in the previous section. However, a simple restriction of the output flow from the dilution box is not possible, as this will cause a harmful back-pressure on the apparatus. To overcome this, a regulator (Figure 4.4) was developed which does not affect the output from the dilution box, but simply wastes the gas not needed. The flow is controlled by operating the valve (see figure) and the final flow is observed by a bullet flow meter.

Gas pressure

The concentration of the calibrated gas is specified in terms of the mixing ratio, and therefore the total pressure is required to calculate the partial pressure of ammonia. By using a calibrated barometer (± 0.2 hPa) placed near the equilibration chamber outlet, the total atmospheric pressure is measured.

FIGURE 4.4: Regulator to control the flow of the calibrated gas.

Temperature

In order to obtain true equilibrium, the temperature has to be uniform throughout the entire setup. Also an important goal of this project is to measure solubilities at different temperatures, requiring the system to have an adjustable, well defined temperature. One possible way of controlling the temperature, is by immersing the equilibrator into a thermostated bath while the liquid is circulated to ensure a uniform temperature.

The final design

The alpha project

After these first considerations, we are now ready to build the equilibrator. The pionering attempt is code named *alpha* and is build from standard laboratory glassware. As shown in Figure 4.5, the liquid phase is circulated using a peristaltic pump that gently leads the liquid down a tube filled with glass rings so as to establish a large liquid surface. The calibrated gas flows in the opposite direction and so encounters the liquid phase in the glass column where the

FIGURE 4.5: Picture of the alpha equilibration system consisting of the gas dilution box (left), the equilibrator (middle) and a peristaltic pump (right).

equilibration is to take place. Prior to this, the calibrated gas is saturated with water vapor by passing it through a flask containing water.

Only few experiments have been made using the alpha chamber as it is replaced by a more professional version as will be presented in a short while. However, the initial experiments have yielded useful experience and stressed out the importance of proper temperature control. Figure 4.6 shows an attempt to saturate a pure aqueous sample with ammonia using the alpha device. During five hours of bubbling, the concentration is still heading uphill and so equilibrium is not established. Also note the distinct drop in temperature. No effort has been made to stabilize the

FIGURE 4.6: Variation in concentration and temperature during gas/liquid equilibration using the alpha chamber.

temperature and as the cold calibrated gas (expanded from high pressure) mixes with the liquid phase, the system cools down. At a level of 288 K the temperature remains stable and in fact the incoming gas now functions as a thermostating device. Advantage of this could be taken by applying a controllable heat source on the incoming gas tubing, and thereby avoid the troublesome task of immersing the complete setup in a water bath. Also this will ensure a completely isothermal gas- and liquid phase.

Knowledge of the gas flow is now used to estimate the efficiency of the equilibrator - *i.e.* the fraction of incoming gas dissolved in the liquid phase. The total volume of water is initially 0.20 l, but is reduced to 0.17 l due to sample taking. This combined with the data in Table 4.2 dictates a maximum aqueous concentration of around 450 nM. That is, if *all* gaseous ammonia is transferred to the water phase during the five hours of bubbling.

x_{NH_3} (ppb)	P_{tot} (atm)	$Flow$ (l/min)	t (min)	V_{tot} (l)	n_{NH_3} (nmol)
1.35	1	4.29	312	1338	76

TABLE 4.2: Experimental conditions during an initial equilibration experiment in the alpha chamber.

As the final concentration is measured to ~ 500 nM the efficiency is calculated to 111%. This result is of course not realistic and is probably caused by experimental uncertainties. Still, it can be concluded that the efficiency of the equilibrator is very close to maximum and so strips off the overall amount of ammonia present in the gaseous phase.

The beta project

Even though the initial experiments performed with the alpha chamber showed promising results, a new equilibrator is considered. From Radiometer A/S we have borrowed a more sophisticated device (Figure 4.7) originally used to calibrate electrodes. It shall here be referred to as the beta chamber. It consists of an equilibration chamber where the gas is bubbled through the liquid phase using a porous membrane. Prior to this, the gas enters a similar, but much smaller chamber, where it is saturated with water vapor. To control the temperature, the two chambers are encapsulated by a second glass wall that allows a continuous flow of thermostated water. Through a connector on one side of the larger chamber, a tubing is fitted to allow water phase samples to be taken using a syringe. These are then injected directly into the OPA system.

Pure water in equilibrium with a 2.8 ppb NH_3 gas will have a total ammonia concentration of approximately 1900 nanomoles per liter. Starting out from $c_{\text{NH}_x}=0$ a substantial equilibration time is needed as the aqueous concentration must build up from zero. In order to shorten the required time, the initial aqueous concentration can be increased to a level near the expected equilibrium concentration. There are less than ten ammonia molecules for each billion gas molecules bubbled through the liquid. Thus, a small excess of NH_x should be removed quite fast and so, to raise the initial concentration in the liquid phase, concentrated ammonia solution is added in appropriate amounts.

FIGURE 4.7: Section of the beta chamber used to bring a gas and liquid phase to equilibrium.

We are now ready to initiate the actual solubility experiments using our new equilibrator. In the following chapter the ammonia-water system is examined in greater detail and we will try to derive the solubility as a function of temperature and salinity.

Chapter 5

Solubility experiments

5.1 Introduction

Since the equilibration system is newly developed a verification of the method is necessary. This is accomplished by measuring the solubility of ammonia in pure water, which is a well described thermodynamic system. A large collection of Henry's law constants for ammonia and many other substances is around [55] and Table 5.1 shows selected values for ammonia:

$\frac{H^\ominus}{(\text{M}\cdot\text{atm}^{-1})}$	$\frac{\Delta H/R}{(\text{K})}$	REFERENCE
59	4100	Sillen and Martell, 1964 [56]
76	3400	Hales and Drewes, 1979 [57]
56	4100	Dasgupta and Dong, 1986 [58]
61	4200	Clegg and Brimblecombe, 1989 [47]
61	3904	Present work

TABLE 5.1: Collection of Henry's law constants and their temperature dependence for ammonia in pure water.

As ammonia dissociates in water, the total solubility is described by the effective Henry's law constant (see page 23). The principle of electro-neutrality (see Appendix B) yields the following expression for the proton concentration in a solution in equilibrium with ammonia gas with partial pressure p_{NH_3} :

$$c_{\text{H}^+} = \sqrt{\frac{K_w}{\frac{H \times p_{\text{NH}_3}}{K_a} + 1}} \quad (5.1)$$

This combined with the effective Henry's law constant (Eq. 5.2) is used to calculate H from the experimentally measured values of partial pressure and total ammonia concentration. As $I \approx 0$ this system can be treated as ideal and the concentration scale can be applied:

$$H_{\text{eff}} = \frac{c_{\text{NH}_x}}{p_{\text{NH}_3}} = H \left(1 + \frac{c_{\text{H}^+}}{K_a}\right) \quad (5.2)$$

The effect of temperature is assumed to be described by the van't Hoff equation (Eq. 2.32) and measuring the solubility at different temperatures allows calculation of $\Delta H/R$.

To calculate the partial pressure of ammonia, one needs to consider the process where the initially dry calibrated gas is saturated with water vapor as it passes through the moisturizer.

$$p_{\text{atm}} = p^{\text{initial}} = p^{\text{final}} \quad \begin{cases} p^{\text{initial}} &= p_0^{\text{initial}} + p_{\text{NH}_3}^{\text{initial}} \\ p^{\text{final}} &= p_0^{\text{final}} + p_{\text{NH}_3}^{\text{final}} + p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

The partial pressure of the dilution gas, ammonia and water are denoted p_0 , p_{NH_3} and $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, respectively. As we perform an isobar equilibration the molefraction of ammonia is constant, but its partial pressure is changed. To calculate the new partial pressure in the water saturated gas, it is necessary to know the vapor pressure of water at the given temperature (Section 2.4). Using the above considerations the following expression is valid

$$p_{\text{NH}_3}^{\text{final}} = (p_{\text{atm}} - p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}) \chi_{\text{NH}_3} \quad (5.4)$$

Here χ_{NH_3} is the mixing ratio of the ammonia gas coming from the equilibrator and p_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure.

5.2 Experimental conditions

To equilibrate the heterogeneous gas/liquid system, the beta chamber (page 42) is used as shown in Figure 5.1. The

FIGURE 5.1: Schematic representation of the equilibration system used to measure the solubility of ammonia in pure water.

solubility is measured at three different temperatures. In the first two experiments (297 K and 284 K) the entire setup is placed in a thermostated room. The 277 K experiment is measured using a refrigerated water bath. The reason for this change in conditions is that attempts to measure low temperature solubilities in the thermostated room cause the gas mixer to malfunction. The system leaks and no ammonia is detected in the aqueous phase - probably because the fittings leak due to contraction in the material. The calibrated gas is guaranteed to work at the chosen temperatures, and so this should not be the source of the problem. Due to this behavior, it is chosen to use a refrigerated bath and so cool only the equilibrator. The bath used is very stable and the temperature variation is less than 0.1°C. A cause of concern in this particular setup, is that the incoming gas is of room temperature and will therefore add heat to the system. To minimize this effect, the gas tubing is wrapped around the cold outlet of the water bath so as to cool the gas before it enters the equilibrator. Next, the gas is led through the thermostated moisturizer where the temperature is yet again lowered - it is now assumed that the gas is in thermal equilibrium with the rest of the system.

With respect to ammonia, the gaseous concentration is 2.8 ppb and the flow is 4-5 liter per minute. As discussed in Section 4.4 it is important to moderate the gas flow - especially at low temperatures. The setup is allowed to equilibrate for 6-10 hours which, as we found earlier, is an appropriate time scale to obtain equilibrium. The total ammonia concentration in the liquid phase is now measured using the OPA-method, while temperature and atmospheric pressure is measured simultaneously.

5.3 Results and discussion

The raw data obtained by the described experiments are tabulated in Appendix B. Figure 5.2 shows a plot of the total ammonia concentration (297 K experiment) as the equilibration proceeds. Eventually, a stable state is reached and it is assumed that equilibrium is established. In contrast, the initial experiments performed using the alfa chamber did not equilibrate (Figure 4.6, page 42).

$T/(K)$	$H/(M \cdot atm^{-1})$	$H^\dagger/(M \cdot atm^{-1})$
297.0	64 ± 3.1	59
284.4	115 ± 1.7	109
277.4	153 ± 6.0	157

TABLE 5.2: Measured solubility of ammonia in pure water. H^\dagger is from Dasgupta and Dong, 1986.

Applying the formulas derived in Appendix B the Henry's law constants shown in Table 5.2 are obtained. The values are in excellent agreement with what is found in the literature. However, the absolute deviation on the 277 K measurements is quite large - possibly due to the problems encountered when measuring at low temperatures. Fitting the measured constants to the van't Hoff equation, yields the temperature dependence and the Henry's law constant at 298 K. The results are plotted in Figure 5.3 together with data from other workers. Clearly, the data from 277 K increases the deviation from the literature values and by omitting it in the fit, closer resemblance to the known data is found. Table 5.3 shows the values of a weighted least-square fit to the van't Hoff equation. In the first case all three experiments are taken into account while in the second only the 297 K and 284 K data are included.

In Section 3.5 we discussed the effect of dissolved sea salt on the solubility of ammonia. At $S=35\%$ the Henry's law constant were estimated (using Monte Carlo simulations) to decrease by 5% relative to pure water. The uncertainties

FIGURE 5.2: The total aqueous ammonia concentration plotted as a function of time for the 297 K experiment. The horizontal dashed line represents the calculated equilibrium concentration using literature values of H and K_a .

$\frac{H^\ominus}{(\text{M/atm})}$	$\frac{\Delta H/R}{(\text{K})}$	DATAPOINTS
63 ± 3.7	3609 ± 338	Three
61	3904	Two

TABLE 5.3: Henry's law constant of ammonia in water at 298 K obtained by fitting experimental data to the Van't Hoff equation. In the first result all three experiments are included in the fit. In the second only the 297 K and 284 K experiments are applied and hence no uncertainties can be calculated.

on the current measurements described in this chapter are 1-5% and thus renders the method slightly too inaccurate to determine the salt effect.

Of course this is true only if the Monte Carlo simulation gives us the right answer. Several attempts made on saline solutions have failed to yield the solubility of ammonia in sea water. This is due to major problems encountered using the gas dilution box which leaks for unexplainable reasons. In future experiments the current difficulties may be overcome by compromising our original goal to measure the solubility at low gaseous concentration (ppb levels). Direct usage of the calibrated gas *i.e.* no dilution box will simplify the setup and so eliminate a source of error not to speak of countless abortive experiments.

But does the gaseous concentration have an influence on the Henry's law constant? Probably not. The values of H shown in Table 5.1 have been determined using high ammonia concentrations and are indeed comparable to the results obtained in the present study. This suggests that the quite troublesome gas dilution method is not worth the effort.

FIGURE 5.3: Experimentally determined Henry's law constants in pure water plotted as a function of temperature. The shown points are the values obtained during this work.

Chapter 6

Field measurements

6.1 Introduction

In the regime of an international project named ANICE the author has participated in a field campaign held in Holland during the summer 1999. The project description reads as follows:

”The ANICE (Atmospheric Nitrogen Inputs into the Coastal Ecosystem) project focus on atmospheric inputs of nitrogen compounds (nitric acid: HNO_3 , nitrate: NO_3^- , ammonia: NH_3 and ammonium: NH_4^+) into the sea and the governing processes that are specific for coastal areas. The overall aim of the ANICE project is to improve the accuracy and performance of model tools used to estimate the atmospheric nitrogen deposition to the sea. Special emphasis is on the chemical and physical processes governing the transformation and deposition of nitrogen compounds in coastal waters. ANICE is a combination of experimental and modeling work. The ANICE study area is the Southern North Sea.”

Among the participants were the National Environmental Research Institute (NERI) and RISØ who focused on the following issues:

- Air-sea fluxes of ammonia and HNO_3
- Chlorophyll A (Algae)
- Nutrients
- Salinity

The author was stationed on the off-shore weather platform *Meetpost Noordwijk* (Figure 6.1) located eight kilometers off the Dutch coast between Amsterdam and Rotterdam¹. The main tasks were measurements of aqueous ammonia, salinity and Chlorophyll A profiles.

Originally, the platform was build to accommodate an illegal TV station as it, at the time being, was located in international waters. Obviously the Dutch authorities were provoked by the daring broadcasts, and so they quickly managed to expand the national boundaries to include the platform. This was the end for the TV station and today the platform accomodates various instruments for monitoring weather and oceanographic phenomena as well as lodging of eighteen operators.

6.2 Aqueous ammonia

In order to investigate the air-sea exchange as well as other marine processes, the aqueous ammonia level is measured. However, the platform facilities do not allow installation of the necessary analytical equipment. Therefore, samples are collected and stored (frozen) for later processing on the shore using the OPA method described in Section 4.2. In addition, samples for nutrient analysis are collected and processed approximately two weeks later at NERI. This analysis is performed by an autoanalyzer (AA) that gives the concentration of SiO_4^{4-} , PO_4^{3-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and NH_x , respectively. The autoanalyser measures the total ammonia concentration using the indophenol blue method (IPB) and thus offers an excellent opportunity to compare with the more accurate OPA method. Figure 6.2 shows a plot of the ammonia concentration measured using the OPA method as a function of the values found using the autoanalyzer.

¹Coordinates: 52.273N 4.297E

FIGURE 6.1: The weather platform Meetpost Noordwijk (MPN) located in the North Sea eight kilometers off the coast between Amsterdam and Rotterdam.

At first glance, the two methods do not produce results directly comparable and a linear regression yields the expression:

$$c_{\text{NH}_x}^{\text{OPA}} = (1.25 \pm 0.06) \times c_{\text{NH}_x}^{\text{AA}} + 307 \pm 73 \quad (6.1)$$

The intercept at 307 nanomoles per liter can be a result of various effects. Firstly, the precision of the autoanalyser is 100 nM and has a detection limit of 200 nM. Thus the calibration of the IPB system can easily lead to a 300 nM shift in concentration. Also the samples analysed using the autoanalyser were stored in plastic vessels, whereas the OPA samples were collected in glass flasks. Ammonia is known to absorb on almost any surface, and polyethylene plastic might be a more willing host than glassware.

As for the slope of 1.25 this can be subscribed to the so called *salt effect*. Sea water contains magnesium ions and other species that influence the buffer capacity. When mixed with the agents in the IPB process, the sample *pH* thus diverges from the pure water samples used to calibrate the system. As the formation of indophenol blue is *pH* dependent, a calibration factor is required to correct for the effect caused by saline samples. Grasshoff *et al.* [59] suggest a value of 1.22 at $S=30\%$ which is in good agreement with our value of 1.25. Note that the composition of buffer solutions used in IPB methods is subject to variations and hence the correction factor is unique to the specific setup. In contrast, to calibrate the OPA system saline standard solutions are applied and the obtained values need no corrections.

6.3 Results and discussion

Before commencing the actual data discussion the reader is referred to Appendix D, where the relevant experimental data are tabulated. Now is also a good chance to emphasize that the explanations given in the following sections are rather speculative as many inputs and transport mechanisms influence the results. The platform is by no means located in an undisturbed area, and thus is strongly affected by antropogenic activities.

Horizontal distribution

To develop accurate atmospheric models of air-sea transfer processes, detailed knowledge of the vertical flux is required. During the campaign, this flux is estimated by performing adjacent measurements of gaseous and aqueous ammonia. Also affecting the flux are possible horizontal gradients in the aqueous concentration. Therefore, when the weather allows it, transect measurements are made by boat around the platform so as to investigate the horizontal distribution. Figure 6.3 shows the concentration of ammonia around the platform and as can be seen, only minor deviations are found. However, between each transect session large variations occur.

The reasons for these variations are far from simple, but one of the major factors is the strong tide present in the area. The location of the platform is between two major river deltas namely Amsterdam and Rotterdam. In the summertime the canals of Amsterdam are frequently “flushed” resulting in a sudden load of nutrients and physical objects to the delta area. Likewise, the Rhine has its delta near Rotterdam and is expected to supply the area with a considerable amount of nutrients. As the direction of the tidal wave is approximately parallel to the coastline, these river outlets are likely to influence the measurements.

FIGURE 6.2: The concentration of ammonia obtained using the OPA and the AA method.

In an ANICE newsletter (Appendix E) the efforts just described have been used to estimate the vertical flux. It is found that at certain conditions where c_{NH_x} is high, the ammonia flux is upward. That is, the ocean emits ammonia to the atmosphere - a fact often omitted in atmospheric transport models.

Tide

Noticeable is the apparent correlation between the observed tide- and c_{NH_x} level as shown in Figure 6.4. This might be partly due to the fact that as the incoming tidal wave moves toward the platform, the lower water layers mix with the upper levels. At calm conditions one or more thermoclines divide the water column into horizontally distributed layers, but at high agitation this stratification diminishes or completely vanishes. As ammonification is occurring mainly at the bottom, a vertical transport mechanism can lead to elevated ammonia levels at the surface. Of course a much less sophisticated explanation of these observations could be that garbage from Amsterdam and Rotterdam surfs the tidal wave. That is, when the tide reaches the coast, sea- and river water mix and when it eventually retreats, the tidal wave is enriched with nutrients.

Chlorophyll A

Another measure subject to our attention is the Chlorophyll A level. This is a useful indication of the overall phytoplankton [60] concentration and is measured using a fluorescence detector. Comparing these data with the total concentration of aqueous ammonia shows an anti correlating trend (Figure 6.5) likely to be caused by the consumption of nutrients during algae growth.

As shown in Figures 6.4 and 6.5 the above phenomenas are not observed throughout all our samples. The Chlorophyll A anti-correlation is seen only from samples 18-40 (a period of 2 days), while the tide correlation is present from samples 1 to 16 (4 days). How these differences arise is uncertain, but might be due to changing weather conditions. Also, one major shortcoming of our aqueous measurements is that they are *point samples* and hence may not be representative for the overall surface concentration. Continuous measurements would allow a much better data resolution and rule out possible random fluctuations. However, at present stage the OPA equipment is not suitable for this purpose, but minor modifications could remedy this matter.

TRANSECT MEASUREMENTS OF AQUATIC AMMONIA AROUND THE PLATFORM

FIGURE 6.3: Horizontal distribution of ammonia around the platform. North, south, east and west are four different stations located 2-3 kilometers from the platform in the given direction.

FIGURE 6.4: Tide level vs. the total ammonia concentration.

FIGURE 6.5: Plot of the total ammonia and Chlorophyll A concentration found in samples taken at the platform.

Conclusion

Starting with the experimental work, it is found that the equilibrator developed is adequate to determine gas solubilities in aqueous solution. However, the accuracy is not sufficient to differentiate pure- and saline water samples in the salt range of natural waters ($S=0-35\%$). Therefore, to determine the solubility as a function of salinity either model work must be applied or the experimental method has to be improved. One way of pursuing the latter approach is by removing the gas dilution box and instead use ammonia gas of ppm levels.

As to the model work, our new approach using Monte Carlo simulations has very accurately described activity coefficients in sea water. By this method the solubility of ammonia in oceanic water ($S=35\%$) has been calculated to decrease 5% relative to pure water. However, the literature values of the solubility constant of ammonia in pure water mutually diverge 5-9%. Thus, to determine the solubility in sea water the choice of the solubility constant is crucial. The computer model is indeed a competitive alternative to the Pitzer model, but at present stage the user interface (or lack of such) is not suitable for the average user. Therefore, work needs to be done on creating a graphical interface - for example via a web page.

The field study carried out in Holland has shown an anti correlation between aqueous ammonia and the algae concentration attributed to biological utilization of nitrogen. Also a connection between ammonia and the tide level is observed. This is possibly due to vertical mixing of the water column or alternatively because of antropogenic sources along the coastline. It is also found that at conditions where the aqueous ammonia level is high, the ocean itself may be a source of nitrogen to the atmosphere. Better understanding of these processes requires continuous measurements of aqueous ammonia, which is currently not possible with our equipment.

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Appendix A

Vapor pressure of sea water

The contour plot shown on the following page can be used to determine the vapor pressure of water over sea water solutions. The plot is based on Equation [2.13](#) and [2.17](#).

Appendix B

Experimental data and calculations

Experimental data

The following table shows the data obtained from the solubility experiments of ammonia in pure water.

$\frac{t}{(\text{min})}$	$\frac{T}{(\text{K})}$	$\frac{c_{\text{NH}_x}}{(\text{nM})}$	$\frac{x_{\text{NH}_3}}{(\text{ppb})}$	$\frac{p_{\text{tot}}}{(\text{hPa})}$	$\frac{p_{\text{aq}}}{(\text{Pa})}$	$\frac{p_{\text{NH}_3}}{(\text{Pa} \cdot 10^4)}$	$\frac{H}{(\text{M/atm})}$
480	277.4	2798	2.8	1001.9	811	2.78	151
555	277.4	3042	2.8	1001.9	811	2.78	(174)
615	277.4	2810	2.8	1001.9	811	2.78	152
675	277.4	2757	2.8	1001.9	811	2.78	147
735	277.4	2907	2.8	1001.9	811	2.78	162
0	283.2	1640	2.8	1016.3	1313	2.81	
76	283.1	2299	2.8	1016.3	1313	2.81	
135	283.6	2543	2.8	1016.3	1313	2.81	114
202	284.1	2343	2.8	1016.3	1313	2.81	(99)
260	284.4	2576	2.8	1016.3	1403	2.81	117
305	284.4	2544	2.8	1016.3	1403	2.81	114
6	295	1303	2.8	1036.6	2645	2.83	
78	296	1524	2.8	1036.5	2810	2.82	
162	297	1918	2.8	1036.4	2985	2.82	62
210	297	2012	2.8	1036.0	2984	2.82	68
264	297	1929	2.8	1036.0	2984	2.82	63

TABLE B.1: Data obtained from equilibrium experiments of the ammonia/water system. The Henry's law constant is calculated as shown in the next section. Values encapsulated in parenthesis are not included in average calculations.

Evaluation of Henry's law constant

The equilibrium experiments yield the total concentration as well as the partial pressure of ammonia. In order to calculate the Henry's law constant the dissociation constant of ammonium is required and in the following section the relevant expressions will be derived.

The principle of electroneutrality dictates that

$$c_{\text{H}^+} + c_{\text{NH}_4^+} = c_{\text{OH}^-} = \frac{K_w}{c_{\text{H}^+}}$$

Combining this with the expression for K_a and H , the proton concentration in an aqueous ammonia solution in equilibrium with ammonia gas is found:

$$c_{\text{H}^+} = \sqrt{\frac{K_w}{\frac{H \times p_{\text{NH}_3}}{K_a} + 1}}$$

Next, to calculate the Henry's law constant this equation is substituted into the expression for the effective Henry's law constant (Eq. 5.2)

$$\left(\frac{K_a c_{\text{NH}_x}}{p_{\text{NH}_3} H} \right) - K_a = \sqrt{\frac{K_w}{\frac{H \times p_{\text{NH}_3}}{K_a} + 1}}$$

As all parameters are known, this can be solved for H and a polynomial is achieved.

Appendix C

Kendall's correlation Test

Theory

Kendall's correlation test is a non-linear method often used to detect trends in time resolved data sets. The basic idea is to sort the data in pairs containing two values; the first larger than the second. It is now tested whether it is likely or not to have k pairs in the set of n points. The test parameter is called *Kendall's Tau*, τ_k :

$$\tau_k = \frac{4 \times k}{n \times (n - 1)} - 1 \quad (\text{C.1})$$

This value is in the interval $[-1; +1]$ where a negative value indicates a decreasing trend; a positive an increasing tendency. To ease the ordering of datasets, a small C-program is written (sourcecode shown below) which calculates n , k and τ_k from a given datafile. For a more detailed discussion of Kendall's correlation test, refer to Christensen [61] or Heilman [62].

Source code

```

/*
NAME:      Kendall's Correlation Test
AUTHOR:    Mikael Lund
DATE:      24.10.00
VERSION:   1.0
LANGUAGE:  C++
*/
#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>

main(int argc, char *argv[] )
{
    int i, n, k, cnt;
    double y, p, tau;
    float data[255];
    FILE *dfile;

    if ( argc != 2 )
        printf("Usage: Kendall datafile\n");
    else {

        /* Initialize array */
        i = 0;
        for (i = 0; i <= 200; i++)
            data[i] = 0 ;
        i = 0;

        /* Read input file */
        if ((dfile = fopen( argv[1], "r")) == NULL)
            printf("File error !\n");
        else {
            while(!feof(dfile)) {
                fscanf(dfile, "%f", &data[i++]);
            }

            fclose(dfile);

            /* Process data */
            n=i-1; i=0; k=0, cnt=0;
            while (cnt <= n ) {
                i=cnt;
                for (i=cnt+1; i<n; i++) {
                    if (data[cnt] > data[i]) {
                        k=k+1;
                        printf("%f  %f\n", data[cnt], data[i] );
                    }
                }
                cnt = cnt + 1;
            }

            /* Evaluate results */
            tau = (4*k) * pow(n * (n-1), -1) -1 ;

            if (n > 10) {
                y = (3*n*(n-1)-12*k) / ( 2* sqrt( n*(n-1)*(n+2.5) ) );
            }
            else {
                y = 0;
                printf("n must be greater than 10 to evaluate y\n");
            }

            /* Show results */
            printf("Kendall Correlation Test \n");
            printf("(By M. Lund, Oct. 2000) \n");
            printf("=====\n");
            printf("Pairs (k) = %d\nTotal (n) = %d\ny = %f\n", k, n, y);
            printf("Kendall's tau = %f\n", -1*tau);
        }
    }
    return 0;
}

```

Appendix D

Platform measurements

The following table contains data from the field measurements made in Holland, 1999. Not all measured parameters are listed, but only those of relevance to the discussion in Chapter 6 are shown. That is aqueous ammonia, Chlorophyll A and the tide level.

Sample	Date ddmmyy	Time hh:mm	OPA c_{NH_x} nmol/l	AA c_{NH_x} nmol/l	Chl A mg/m^3	Tide cm
1	200899	14:30	709	200	32.5	-16
2	210899	02:00	1066	510		4
3	210899	09:00	1022	460	25.5	4
4	210899	11:20	1126	600		62
5	210899	17:40	207		3.6	-46
6	220899	12:30	3264	2260	15.2	58
7	220899	19:40	1586	810	24.2	-39
8	220899	22:55	3122	2390		-6
9	230899	01:35	3564	2570		52
10	230899	08:10	642	260	17.5	-43
11	230899	10:30	2230	1520		-29
12	230899	16:05	2302	1530	18.4	39
13	230899	23:25	1627	1050	23.5	-33
14	240899	08:05	2016	1290	20.9	-27
15	240899	13:20	1590	680		30
16	240899	22:30	932	430		-61
17	250899	08:05		730		
18	250899	11:05	895	480	16.5	-49
19	250899	12:05	635	210	17.0	-47
20	250899	12:35	477		17.5	-39
21	250899	13:00	640	1560	17.3	-25
22	250899	13:30	629		16.8	-4
23	250899	14:00	592	210	23.0	25
24	250899	14:30	447		24.3	55
25	250899	15:30	585			88
26	250899	16:30	759	570	18.2	77
27	250899	17:30	732		19.0	46
28	250899	18:00	887		16.2	28
29	250899	18:30	715	640	16.5	10
30	250899	20:30	864			-37
31	260899	06:00	739			53
32	260899	09:00	181			-12
33	260899	10:30	940	880		-33
34	260899	12:00	819			-50
35	260899	14:35	412			11
36	260899	17:00	132	110		84
37	260899	20:00	150		24.7	-26
38	260899	21:35	121			-37
39	270899	00:35	776			-67
40	270899	08:05	177			8

Appendix E

Newsletter: Ammonia deposition in a coastal area.

Appendix F

Manuscript: Activity coefficients in sea water using Monte Carlo simulations